

Study Data Dictionary and Coding Manual

Project Title:: Post-traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) Screening in a High-Volume Postpartum Primary Care Setting using the Kurdish version of the PTSD Checklist for the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (PCL-5)]

Date: January 2026

Software Compatibility: Excel / SPSS

1. Age (in years)
2. Parity
3. Gestational Age at delivery
4. Education: (1)Non-Educated (2)Primary school (3) secondary school (4)University
5. Employment: (1) Employed (2) Unemployed
6. Method of Conceiving :(1) Spontaneous (2) Primary subfertility (3) secondary subfertility
7. Complications during pregnancy or labour : (0)no complication (1) Medical disorder during pregnancy(DM ,hypertension) (2) Hospital admission at antenatal period(3) APH (4) IUGR (5) Anaemia (6) Multiple gestation (7) PROM or PPROM
8. Mode of delivery:(1) spontaneous vaginal delivery (2) induction of labor (3) elective CS (4) emergency CS
9. Pain management during labour: (1) Satisfied (2)Unsatisfied
- 10.Complications at post-partum :(0)no complication (1)PPH (2) Blood transfusion (3) Any surgical procedure (4) admissions to hospital for causes related to pregnancy or not
- 11.Outcome of delivery: (1)Alive baby given directly to family (2)Stillbirth (3) Admission to NCU
- 12.Maternal mental health: (0)negative past psychological history (1)History of psychological problem prior to pregnancy (2) Prenatal depression
- 13.Trauma history and PTSD history:(1)Yes (2) No

- 14.Q1: Unwanted upsetting memories about the trauma: 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe
- 15.Q2: Bad dreams or nightmares related to the trauma: 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe
- 16.Q3: Reliving the traumatic event or feeling as if it were actually happening again: 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe
- 17.Q4: Feeling very emotionally upset when reminded of the trauma: 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe
- 18.Q5: Having physical reactions when reminded of the trauma: 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe:
- 19.Q6: Trying to avoid thoughts or feelings related to the trauma: 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe
- 20.Q7: Trying to avoid activities, situations, or places that remind you of the trauma or that feel: 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe:
- 21.Q8: Not being able to remember important parts of the trauma: Not being able to remember important parts of the trauma: 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a

week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe

22.Q9: Seeing yourself, others, or the world in a more negative way:0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe

23.Q10: Blaming yourself or others (besides the person who hurt you) for what happened: 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe

24.Q11: Having intense negative feelings like fear, horror, anger, guilt, or shame: 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe

25.Q12: Losing interest or not participating in activities you used to do :0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe

26.Q13: Feeling distant or cut off from others: 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe

27.Q14: Having difficulty experiencing positive feelings: 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe

28.Q15: Acting more irritable or aggressive with others : 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe

29.Q16: Taking more risks or doing things that might cause you or others harm 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated

"two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe

30.Q17: Being overly alert or on guard:0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe

31.Q18: Being jumpy or more easily startled0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe

32.Q19: Having trouble concentrating:0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe

33.Q20: Having trouble falling or staying asleep: 0 indicated "not at all, 1 indicated "once a week or less/a little, 2 indicated "two to three times a week/somewhat, 3 indicated four to five times a week/very much, 4 indicated six or more times a week/severe